

[original insight]

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The qubit permutation semigroup

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August 3, 2022

Abstract

We propose the equivalence between one Wolfram model and the qubit permutation semigroup.

keywords: qubit, Wolfram model, permutation semigroup, quantum time

The most updated version of this white paper is available at

<https://osf.io/qkdxv/download>

<https://zenodo.org/record/6687742>

Introduction

1. This white paper is the *sequel* of [1], inspired by [2], and it can be best understood if one is familiar to the **Wolfram model** [2–5].

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Notation

2. qubit := quantum bit
3. (a, b) := ordered pair
4. (ab) := cycle notation
5. r, R_1, R_2 := binary relations
6. \cong := bijection
7. \circ := operation of composition
8. tic, tac := each permutation of the qubit semigroup

Qubit

9.
$$|\psi\rangle = a|0\rangle + b|1\rangle := \text{qubit}$$
10. $a, b \in \mathbb{C}, \quad |a|^2 + |b|^2 = 1$
11. $R_1 = \{(0, 1)\}, \quad R_2 = \{(1, 0)\}$
12. The elements of R_1 and R_2 are assigned with the following meaning:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &:= |0\rangle, \\ 1 &:= |1\rangle. \end{aligned}$$

The Symmetric Group

13. [6, 7]
14.
$$(S(A), \circ) := \text{symmetric group on } A$$

15. $S(A) = \{f : A \cong A\} :=$ set of permutations of A

16. $A \neq \emptyset$

$S_2 \setminus S_1$

17. $A_2 = \{0, 1\}, \quad A_1 = \{0\}$

18. $S_2(A_2) = \{(0), (0, 1)\}, \quad S_1(A_1) = \{(0)\}$

19. $S := S_2(A_2) \setminus S_1(A_1) = \{(0, 1)\}$

20. $f, g, h := (01)$

21. $(f \circ g) \circ h = ?$

22. $((f \circ g) \circ h)(0) = (f \circ g) \circ h(0) = (f \circ g)(1) = f(g(1)) = f(0) = 1$

23. $((f \circ g) \circ h)(1) = (f \circ g) \circ h(1) = (f \circ g)(0) = f(g(0)) = f(1) = 0$

24. $(f \circ g) \circ h = (01)$

25. $f \circ (g \circ h) = ?$

26. $(f \circ (g \circ h))(0) = f \circ (g \circ h)(0) = f \circ g(h(0)) = f \circ g(1) = f(g(1)) = f(0) = 1$

27. $(f \circ (g \circ h))(1) = f \circ (g \circ h)(1) = f \circ g(h(1)) = f \circ g(0) = f(g(0)) = f(1) = 0$

28. $f \circ (g \circ h) = (01)$

29. Therefore $(f \circ g) \circ h = f \circ (g \circ h)$.

The qubit permutation semigroup

30.

$(Q, \circ) :=$ qubit permutation semigroup

31.

$(P, \circ) :=$ group of all the permutations of R

32. $R = \{R_1, R_2\}$

33. $P = \{(R_1), (R_1R_2)\}$

34. $Q = P \setminus \{(R_1)\} = \{(R_1R_2)\}$

35. $r = \{(R_1, R_2)\}$

36. $R_1 = \{(0, 1)\}, R_2 = \{(1, 0)\}$

37. $0 := |0\rangle, 1 := |1\rangle$

The equivalence

38. **Proposition.** *The Wolfram model r is equivalent to the qubit permutation semigroup.*

Quantum time

39. According to [1],

(i) classical time := map between relations,

(ii) quantum time := arrow within a graph.

The emergence of quantum gravity

40. If the “tic tac” of the **qubit permutation semigroup** *originates time itself*, then due to the Heisenberg uncertainty principle, **energy is created** and *it generates the source of gravity* at the quantum level.
41. **The “tic tac” of the spin generates curved spacetime.**
42. *Insight: Check if the definition of topological cover fits in this context.*

Next steps

43. Provide a semigroup algebraic approach on
 - (i) the tensorial product of two qubits;
 - (ii) entanglement;
 - (iii) quantum teleport;
 - (iv) the collapse in the measurement problem.

Final Remarks

44. We believe the equation [1]

$\text{quantum time} = \textit{the arrow in the qubit graph approach}$

can give us a hint on the quantum nature of spacetime.

Open Invitation

Review, add content, and co-author this white paper [8,9].

Join the **Open Mathematics Collaboration**.

Send your contribution to mplobo@uft.edu.br.

Open Science

The **latex file** for this *white paper* together with other *supplementary files* are available in [10, 11].

How to cite this paper?

<https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/qkdxv>

<https://zenodo.org/record/6687742>

Acknowledgements

+ **Center for Open Science**

<https://cos.io>

+ **Open Science Framework**

<https://osf.io>

+ **Zenodo**

<https://zenodo.org>

+ **The Wolfram Physics Project**

<https://www.wolframphysics.org>

Agreement

The author agrees with [9].

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